

C=N Stretching Frequency in I. R. Spectra of Conjugated Aromatic Imines

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It has been established that chemistry of imines is somewhat similar to that of aldehydes and ketones¹. Spectral studies have also been carried on in case of non-conjugated imines. The $>C=N$ -stretching frequency is reported in the region $1618\text{--}1639\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in solid state and $1618\text{--}1645\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in chloroform solution²; this band occurs in the high frequency side of the aromatic or olefinic bands near 1600 cm^{-1} . In aldehydes and ketones the $>C=O$ stretching frequency is appreciably affected by conjugation and inductive effects of groups. In order to draw a comparison of the systems $>C=\overset{\overset{|}{C}}{\underset{\underset{|}{O}}{C}}=O$ and $>C=\overset{\overset{|}{C}}{\underset{\underset{|}{N}}{C}}=N$, U.V. absorption spectroscopy has been employed³. There seems to be no report of such comparison of the I.R. spectra in acyclic derivatives. Presently we have reported the I.R. spectra of a few conjugated imines.

The conjugated imines were prepared (1-7) by condensing cinnamaldehyde with appropriate aromatic amines in ethanol. The cyano N-cinnamylidene aniline was prepared from cinnamyl N-phenyl nitron by the addition of hydrocyanic acid (C.H.N. % 82.75, 5.17, 12.06, calcd. C.H.N. % 82.50, 5.06, 12.08 found) which in turn was obtained as earlier described by us⁴.

The I.R. absorption spectra of these imines were recorded as KBr pellets. The absorption band characteristics of the $>C=N$ -bond is found to be of high intensity and appears in the region $1610\text{--}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as can be seen from the data given below:

N-cinnamyl idene aniline	Frequency 1620 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>p</i> -Cl "	1625 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>p</i> -CH ₃ "	1621 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>p</i> -Br "	1610 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ "	1620 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ "	1628 cm^{-1}
N- " <i>m</i> -NO ₂ "	1610 cm^{-1}
N- " Cyanoimine	1615 cm^{-1}

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4. Nazar Singh and Suresh Mohan, *Chem. Comm. (London)*, 1968, **14**, 787.

These data indicate that conjugation does not have much effect on the $>C=N$ -frequency. In the case of the $>C=O$ frequency there is generally a decrease due to conjugation. Electron withdrawing groups are attached to $>C=O$ group generally increase the $>C=O$ frequency. In the imines studied presently substitution by cyanide group does not effect the $>C=N$ -absorption appreciably. We find that $>C=N$ -frequency in these imines can be detected even in the presence of $>C=C$ bond without much difficulty.

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